

ISic3450

I.Sicily inscription 3450

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta

Coordinates

37.307741, 14.710805

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5196

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Λάπος Σαβίνου

2. πρεσβυτέρου

3. ΤΕΥΤΑ[]ΚΑ

4. αίων[]

Apparatus

Text from edition of Cordano 2005

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491430

EDCS 55702036

Bibliography

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